

Retrospective Study on the Completeness of Anaesthesia Records at a University Teaching Hospital in 2017, August

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Introduction: Anaesthesia record, a valuable tool in medicolegal defence, contains pre, intra and post-operative information that facilitates delivery of effective, quality care. Incomplete records depriving valuable information observed in the hospital considered created grounds for this investigation.

Objectives: To assess percentage frequency of completion of selected fields in the anaesthesia record.

Methods: Anaesthesia records of 427 patients operated under general anaesthesia in August, 2017 were analysed. A checklist based on the anaesthesia record was used for data collection.

Results: Out of 427 bed head tickets, 40.3% (172/427) lacked anaesthesia records. Fields exclusively to anaesthesia record; anaesthetic drugs, venous access, ET tube, ventilation, position and circuit showed completion rates between 77%-94%. Analysis of the fields of current drugs, allergies, previous anaesthetics of a patient's Anaesthesia record with a positive medical, allergy and past surgical history revealed 64% (54/84), 45% (10/22), 54% (57/105) of incomplete records respectively.

Conclusion: Overall, anaesthesia records are not given due significance though anaesthetists show a positive attitude towards intra operative information which is exclusive to them. High value of the form is depreciated due to lack of completion which may be due to its format. Therefore, development of a user-friendly form is suggested.

References

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